

sheath rot, sheath blotch, glume discoloration, and brown spot. Pale yellow mottle virus may be serious in the future.

Rice insect pests identified in Liberia include caseworm *Nymphula depunctalis* (in wetland fields only); Diopsis *Diopsis thoracica*; stem borers *Maliarpha separatella*, *Chilo zacconius*, and *Sesamia calamistis*; whorl maggot *Hydrellia prosternalis*; leaf-feeding beetle *Epilachna*

sp; grain-sucking insects *Stenocorys* sp., *Aspavia* sp., and *Leptocoryza* sp.; and for stored grains, the common rice weevil *Sitophilus oryzae*. Observations on their incidence in various parts of Liberia indicate that the following can be serious in some situations: caseworm, stem borer, Diopsis, and grain-sucking insects.

The following varieties, which could be used in future breeding programs, have been identified as resistant to some of

the important pests: IR1416-131-5 and LAC 23 to blast; Tetep, IR4547-6-1-1, IR2035-290-2-1-1, and IAC1500 to leaf scald; Suakoko 8, IR2058-435-3-1, IR2071-105-2, IR2071-586-5-6, IR4422-6-2, and B462b-Pn-31-1 to brown spot; Brengut, BW78, BKN6323, and ROK 2 to caseworm; IR5, Suakoko 8, Gissi 27, LAC23, OS6, M55, 63-83, IR1754-F₅B-23, and IRAT 13 to the common rice weevil. ■

Yield losses caused by sheath rot

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A study was made of the yield losses caused by sheath rot damage on crops raised during the normal kharif in Thanjavur district, Tamil Nadu, where the disease has a maximum incidence of 65%.

In 1979 kharif, 100 diseased panicles were collected from the first tillers of hills in uniformly fertilized bulk plots of 10 rice cultivars. The grain yields from the panicles with different grades of

Yield losses caused by sheath rot disease, Tamil Nadu, India.

Variety	Grade 1 yield (g/sample)	Yield loss (%) at disease grade			
		3	5	7	9
ADT31	265.9	+0.5	13.2	48.1	81.6
IET2881	263.9	2.6	21.5	58.5	87.2
Pusa 4-1-11-1	202.2	+0.5	17.3	63.9	85.2
AD6380	272.1	8.1	40.4	65.0	89.5
AD5620	236.4	6.8	21.3	63.4	81.8
AD54-1	255.3	7.9	31.1	58.6	86.6
AS3827	277.8	4.2	20.9	55.7	83.6
CRM10-5747	228.3	3.5	21.2	61.5	85.2
Bhavani	308.9	2.7	16.1	58.0	80.8
IR20	262.0	7.4	35.7	65.3	89.8

sheath rot infection were recorded; the yield losses are shown in the table.

At disease grade 3, no yield loss was

observed in ADT31 and Pusa 4-1-11-1; in AD5620, IR20, AD54-1, and AD6380 the loss was 7-8%. ■

A greenhouse screening technique for ragged stunt resistance

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Ragged stunt virus disease is transmitted by the brown planthopper (BPH) in a persistent manner. Climatic factors that affect the BPH population may also affect disease resistance scores in field screening. The disease symptoms are often unclear until the plant's heading stage in the field. Therefore, scientists need screening techniques that both eliminate the effect of climatic factors and allow detection of disease symptoms at the seedling stage.

In a project to develop such a screening technique for ragged stunt resistance, BPH originally collected at the Muara Experimental Farm, CRIA, were

Procedures for inoculating plants by means of viruliferous insects for ragged stunt screening. CRIA, Indonesia.

reared in a screen cage for 4 years. Ragged stunt virus, originally isolated from a diseased rice plant collected at Pandeglang, Java, in 1976, was maintained on the rice variety TNI or

Pelita I-1.

Twenty-five BPH females were allowed to lay eggs for 1 day on an infected plant covered with a plastic cylindrical cage. The eggs began to